

MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE OF INTERMEDIATE LEARNERS THROUGH PROJECT WAYS

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Mathematics Performance of Intermediate Learners through Project Ways

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Abstract

Intermediate learners are struggling to understand and analyze the material in their classes. There was a significant decline of 2.25% in learners' GWA (Grade Weighted Average) after the implementation of modular remote learning, indicating a notable decline in their academic performance. In order to address the existing disparities, it is suggested that the materials be streamlined and supplemented by video lectures and audio recordings, online discussions, local training sessions, and home visits. With that, this study was crafted to enhance the mathematics performance of intermediate learners in San Miguel Dao I Elementary School through Worksheets, Audio and Video Conferencing, YouTube links, and Self-Assessment (Project WAYS). A quantitative research design was used in this study which used quasi-experimental research design. The research took place at San Miguel Dao I Elementary School. The study's participants were intermediate learners (Grades 4, 5, and 6) for the school year 2022-2023. A pretest and posttest were used to collect data. After establishing research communication with respective DepEd officials, the researcher personally facilitated the examination. This covered the third quarter of school year 2022-2023. The data was analyzed using a paired t-test in Microsoft Excel Data Analysis Tool Pack. Before the implementation of Project WAYS, intermediate learners performed poorly in mathematics which shows that learners did not meet the expectations. Meanwhile after the implementation of Project WAYS, intermediate learners still performed poorly in mathematics which shows that learners still did not meet the expectations. However, if these results will be compared to the pretest before the implementation of Project WAYS, a better performance of intermediate learners can be traced. Additionally, the study has identified a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results paving the way to reject the null hypothesis and showing proof that Project WAYS is effective in enhancing the mathematical academic performance of intermediate learners in San Miguel Dao I Elementary School. The findings paved the way to provide more support mechanisms for the enhancement of academic performance of learners for it was backed-up with the results that learning accompanied with suitable support mechanisms would ensure wholesome accomplishments in the part of the learners.

Keywords: *audio and video conferencing, mathematical performance, self-assessment, worksheets, YouTube links*

Introduction

The inclusion of mathematics education in the K–12 curriculum in the Philippines is of utmost importance. Its objective is to improve the overall quality of education and develop graduates who possess the necessary abilities for the modern day (Mamolo & Sugano, 2020). The K–12 curriculum aims to equip students with a well-rounded education that adequately qualifies them for the requirements of the contemporary labor market (Department of Education, 2010; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2017; Barquilla & Cabili, 2021; Limon, 2021). The quality of mathematics education is crucial for the success of K–12 programs (Saxton et al., 2014; Lo et al., 2017). Recent studies have identified a notable deficiency in mathematics education in the Philippines, as evidenced by the large number of students who are unable to reach the required level of competency (Lituanas et al., 2001; Sánchez-Cabrero et al., 2021; Haw et al., 2021). Moreover, educators encounter multiple obstacles when it comes to providing high-quality mathematics education. These issues encompass insufficient mastery of the subject matter, scarcity of resources, and absence of support (Harris et al., 2011; Bragg et al., 2021; Haw et al., 2021). Hence, it is imperative to tackle these issues and enhance the caliber of mathematics education in order to accomplish the goals of the K–12 curriculum.

Meanwhile, intermediate learners are having difficulty comprehending and analyzing the contents of their lessons. Dargo and Dimas' 2021 study found that a 2.25% fall in learners' GWA following the introduction of modular remote learning indicates a substantial deterioration in their academic performance. Distance learning that is modular fosters family bonds, promotes individual learning, and is cost-effective. However, it adds to the stress of working parents because there is little teacher-learner interaction, learners lack socialization with other children, and they are not exposed to substantial school activities but are instead exposed to numerous distractions at home. To bridge the gaps, it is proposed that materials be simplified and complemented by video lectures and audio recordings, online mediations, neighborhood training, and house visits.

It is their request to seek additional assistance to help them understand the lesson. Furthermore, MPS (Mean Percentage Score) results of their summative tests in the 2nd quarter include 45.00, 42.81, and 60.31, respectively, which are alarming because they reflect the poor performance of intermediate learners in mathematics.

Meanwhile, Bote (2022) has mentioned that the use of a learning resource package in teaching and learning numeracy has been found to be effective and should be adapted and used in the lesson. Thus, numeracy learning resource packages are effective instructional materials that learners can use to improve their numeracy performance. With that in mind, the proponent of this intervention intends to bridge the gap between the learners' learning of mathematics and the difficulties they are experiencing.

Everyone finds it difficult to pick up new abilities. In an official learning environment, where your focus is diverted in a dozen different places at once, it is even more challenging. Although learning in a classroom has numerous benefits, it is not the most natural way for people to learn. Therefore, we need to figure out how to use technology in a way that promotes engagement and helps with learning. Technology, Villasoto (2023), may be utilized to make learning easier, faster, and more engaging for both teachers and students when used properly.

In 2022, Allison Academy released a piece discussing the advantages of using technology in the classroom for both instructors and younger students. Put another way, learners now have the chance to make studying much easier and more pleasurable thanks to the unexpected appearance of a wide variety of devices and the internet. The main advantages of technology in education include increasing the interactivity of learning and teaching, giving teachers and students access to a limitless supply of current information and data from a variety of sources, teaching students how to use technology, reducing the cost of education, and enabling teachers and students to learn at different times and simultaneously.

This paper aimed to enhance the mathematical academic performance of intermediate learners at San Miguel Dao I Elementary School. In this study, the researcher proposes to utilize worksheets, audio and video conferencing, YouTube links, and self-assessment (Project WAYS) as an intervention to bridge the identified gap. This research tested the effectiveness of Project WAYS as an intervention material for intermediate learners to improve their mathematical academic performance. This was held at San Miguel Dao I Elementary School, covering the 3rd quarter of the school year 2022-2023. Thus, worksheets, audio and video conferencing, YouTube links, and self-assessment (Project WAYS) are being conceptualized. This was a school-wide initiative to provide support mechanisms for enhancing the mathematical academic performance of intermediate learners.

Research Questions

This study generally aimed to enhance the mathematical academic performance of intermediate learners in San Miguel Dao I Elementary School through Worksheets, Audio and Video Conferencing, YouTube links, and Self-Assessment (Project WAYS) in the school year 2022 – 2023. Specifically, this aimed to answer the questions as follows:

1. What is the mathematical academic performance of intermediate learners based on the pretest scores before the implementation of Project WAYS?
2. What is the mathematical academic performance of intermediate learners based on the posttest scores after the implementation of Project WAYS?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results of intermediate learners before and after the implementation of Project WAYS?

Literature Review

The COVID-19 pandemic has thrown a wrench in the educational system, allowing the country to shift away from face-to-face teaching and toward a variety of alternative learning forms. Following a series of planning and pilot deployments of various learning modalities, the new normal in education was introduced in order to sustain and offer quality education despite the ongoing pandemic catastrophe. The Philippines is currently transitioning to a new normal type of education, with educators' ongoing innovations and the active participation of other stakeholders driving its success. The teacher is in charge of keeping track of the student's progress. Learners can communicate with the teacher via e-mail, phone, text message, instant messaging, and other channels. When possible, the instructor should pay home visits to kids who require remediation or support.

Mathematics instructors have found it challenging to teach mathematics due to the nature of contact with learners and the availability of material delivery during instruction. Mathematics was traditionally taught primarily through face-to-face interaction, with learners interacting with both the materials presented and with one another in the classroom. Facing the new normal of education in mathematics instruction is crucial for teachers who use various distance learning modes. It is challenging to convey a teacher's knowledge to pupils while taking into account the person's ability to reach out, particularly to learners who cannot afford a cellphone or even enough to connect with them, and vice versa, as Dampog have mentioned in 2021.

Furthermore, according to the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), the Philippines achieved a math score of 297. In mathematics, only 1 percent of Filipino pupils achieved the high criterion, which entails the application of conceptual understanding to solve problems. They may use their conceptual understanding of whole numbers to solve two-step word puzzles. They demonstrate comprehension of the number line, multiples, factors, rounding numbers, and operations involving fractions and decimals. Furthermore, students are able to solve uncomplicated measuring problems. They exhibit comprehension of the geometric properties of forms and angles. Students have the ability to analyze and use the data presented in tables and various types of graphs to solve problems.

Furthermore, a total of six percent of Filipino pupils achieved the intermediate criterion, indicating their ability to apply fundamental mathematical concepts in straightforward scenarios. Conversely, 19% of Filipino pupils demonstrated proficiency below the established standards, indicating that they possess only rudimentary arithmetic skills. They possess the ability to do addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division operations on whole numbers that consist of one or two digits. They possess the ability to

resolve uncomplicated word problems. They possess a basic understanding of elementary fractions and often encounter geometric figures. Students possess the ability to comprehend and accomplish basic tasks involving bar graphs and tables. The results are concerning, as Filipinos ranked lowest among 58 countries in a math assessment for Grade 4 students.

The teaching-learning process in the new normal of education, according to Aksan (2021), has an impact on learners' performance, particularly when adopting a modular set-up of learning in mathematics. Because education is no longer confined to the classroom, parents have become educators' collaborators. As home facilitators, parents play an essential role. Their main job in modular learning is to connect with and guide the youngster, according to FlipScience in 2020. According to Bijeesh (2017), if learners are not surrounded by teachers and classmates who remind them of their obligations, they are more likely to become sidetracked and lose track of deadlines. Furthermore, Dangle and Sumaoang (2020) revealed the main challenges that arose during the implementation of distance learning, such as a lack of budget for module creation and delivery, learners struggling to complete module tasks, and parents lacking academic knowledge to guide their children.

Mijares (2022) discovered in a recent study that teachers employed multiple teaching styles, ICT skills, assessment and evaluation skills, interpersonal skills, and self-management abilities to assist learners' mathematical learning. The perceived attitudes of learners toward mathematics have little bearing on their academic achievement in mathematics. A closer examination of the correlational analysis results reveals that learners' perceived attitudes toward mathematics, such as (a) motivation and support, (b) anxiety in learning, and (c) self-efficacy in learning mathematics, have no significant effect on their academic performance in mathematics. Furthermore, when parents or guardians apply mentoring tactics at home, learners' academic performance in mathematics improves. This is based on the findings of a correlational analysis, which revealed that only mentoring strategies (a) had a significant impact on the academic performance of learners in mathematics of the four parental involvement strategies (a) mentoring strategies, (b) parental involvement strategies, (c) awarding and recognition strategies, and (d) awarding scheme strategies.

With this in mind, the proponent of this intervention wanted to bridge the gap between learning mathematics and the learners' challenges by implementing support mechanisms that improve the learners' academic performance in mathematics.

Methodology

Rogers and Revesz's work in 2019 mentioned that quasi-experimental research designs look for a relationship between independent and dependent variables. In other words, it is expected that the independent variable will cause some variation or change in the dependent variable. As a result, the quasi-experimental research design was considered appropriate for use in this study for it will measure on the change of behavior in the independent variable, that is, the enhancement of the mathematical academic performance of intermediate learners based on the posttest scores after the implementation of Project WAYS.

The study took place at San Miguel Dao I Elementary School. San Miguel Dao I Elementary School was listed as one of the schools with poor math performance. The location was chosen because recent data in the MPS of the first and second periodical examinations show that intermediate learners perform poorly. According to the current study's findings, MPS summative test scores in the second quarter were 45.00, 42.81, and 60.31, respectively, which is concerning because it demonstrates intermediate learners' poor performance in mathematics. As a result, San Miguel Dao I Elementary School was chosen as the locale of the study during the third quarter of the school year 2022-2023.

Specifically, there are 19, 22, and 16, with a total of 57 intermediate learners in the population. The entire population was used. In total, 57 intermediate learners served as the participants of this study. Pretest and posttest were used to collect the necessary data based on the presented research problems. The research instruments were also validated by the local school principal, the principal in charge of Mathematics, and a mathematics master teacher. Similarly, after piloting, internal consistency and reliability was established using the Cronbach Alpha rate of 0.05, which indicates item reliability.

The study began with the establishment of research communications among the DepEd personnel involved. Taking into account the MPS test results from the second quarter periodical examination, as well as the number of intermediate learners in the local, the researcher then administered a pretest to the entire population of 57, using a validated and reliability-checked pretest for Grades 4, 5, and 6. The groups went through Project WAYS using worksheets with contextualized answer sheets, audio and video conferencing to clarify concepts, YouTube links for additional information, and self-assessment for evaluation. The posttest was facilitated after a quarter of the intervention has been facilitated.

After gathering all relevant information, the data was tallied and presented in tables for statistical treatment and quantitative analysis, with the results serving as the foundation for improving Project WAYS' performance in the coming quarters. Paired t-test was used in this study to determine whether there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results of intermediate learners before and after the implementation of Project WAYS.

In general, morality is a set of written and unwritten rules that govern our expectations of ourselves and others. They essentially determine how and why we treat others. While there is broad agreement on some moral values, there are significant differences in how these values should be applied in practice. During the study period, the following ethical principles were established to ensure that learners' dignity and well-being are always protected. Furthermore, all research data will be kept strictly confidential throughout the

course of the study. With that, all the key information of the learners was then kept in privacy so to establish utmost confidentiality.

Results and Discussion

1. Mathematical Academic Performance of Intermediate Learners Based on the Pretest Results Before the Implementation of Project WAYS

Table 1. *Mathematical Academic Performance of Intermediate Learners Based on the Pretest Results Before the Implementation of Project WAYS*

Grade Level	Mean of Scores	Rating	Interpretation
Grade Four	12.22	30.55	Did Not Meet Expectations
Grade Five	10.32	20.64	Did Not Meet Expectations
Grade Six	14.25	23.75	Did Not Meet Expectations
Overall	12.26	24.52	Did Not Meet Expectations

Grading Scale: As per DepEd Order 8, Series 2016, Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program

Outstanding (O): 90-100

Very Satisfactory (VS): 85-89

Satisfactory (S): 80-84

Fairly Satisfactory (FS): 75-79

Did Not Meet Expectations (DNME): 75 and below

Table 1 depicts the mathematical academic performance of intermediate learners based on the pretest results before the implementation of Project WAYS. It further shows that before implementation, intermediate learners performed poorly in mathematics having an overall mean of 12.26, which shows that learners did not meet the expectations. This data was supported by Pan and Sana in 2021 which reiterated that pretesting entails taking practice tests prior to learning information rather than after. This method is also known as an erroneous creation or pre-questioning. Due to the fact that the pretest contains information that the learners still need to learn, it is not always possible to ensure that they will perform well on the pretest. Because of this, it is still permissible for the learners to have a low performance in the pretest.

2. Mathematical Academic Performance of Intermediate Learners Based on the Pretest Results Before the Implementation of Project WAYS

Table 2. *Mathematical Academic Performance of Intermediate Learners Based on the Posttest Results After the Implementation of Project WAYS*

Grade Level	Mean of Scores	Rating	Interpretation
Grade Four	21.39	53.48	Did Not Meet Expectations
Grade Five	17.86	35.72	Did Not Meet Expectations
Grade Six	23.81	39.68	Did Not Meet Expectations
Overall	21.02	42.04	Did Not Meet Expectations

Grading Scale: As per DepEd Order 8, Series 2016, Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program

Outstanding (O): 90-100

Very Satisfactory (VS): 85-89

Satisfactory (S): 80-84

Fairly Satisfactory (FS): 75-79

Did Not Meet Expectations (DNME): 75 and below

Table 2 shows the mathematical academic performance of intermediate learners based on the posttest results after the implementation of Project WAYS. It further shows that after implementation, intermediate learners still performed poorly in mathematics having an overall mean of 21.02, which shows that learners still did not meet the expectations. However, if these results will be compared to the pretest before the implementation of Project WAYS, a better performance of intermediate learners can be traced. In 2021, Pan and Sana supported this idea and emphasized the effectiveness of post testing that seemed to depend on how well learners could apply what they had been taught. According to this point of view, the excellent performance of the learners may be linked back to their talents in applying the information that was taught to them; therefore, learners will perform well on the posttest because it incorporates material that was previously taught.

3. Significant Difference Between the Mathematical Academic Performance of Intermediate Learners Before and After the Implementation of Project WAYS

Table 3. *Significant Difference Between the Mathematical Academic Performance of Intermediate Learners Before and After the Implementation of Project WAYS*

Grade Level	Mean of Scores		p-value	Difference	Remarks
	Pretest	Posttest			
Grade Four	12.22	21.39	0.00	Significant	Reject H ₀
Grade Five	10.32	17.86	0.00	Significant	
Grade Six	14.25	23.81	0.00	Significant	
Average	12.26	21.02		Significant	

Table 3 presents the results of the paired t-test employed in order to assess whether or not there is a statistically significant difference between the pretest and the posttest. The table also provides information on the improvement in performance that the learners demonstrated in the pretest and the posttest. Initially, in the pretest conducted, the learners' performance did not meet expectations having a mean of 14.25. Meanwhile, after going through the intervention, these learners were able to improve their mathematical academic performance in the posttest, with a mean of 23.81.

Furthermore, after the use of the paired t-test to compute for a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results, the computed p-value of the study is less than 0.0001. Considering the alpha of 0.05, and by comparing the results of p-value that is less than 0.0001, the study has identified a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results, for it is a rule that in order to conclude a significant difference among the two variables, its computed p-value should be lower than its given alpha of 0.05. Paving the way to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, it can be concluded that Project WAYS is effective in enhancing the mathematical academic performance of intermediate learners in San Miguel Dao I Elementary School.

Conclusions

The following are concluded based from the findings of the study: Before the implementation of Project WAYS, intermediate learners performed poorly in mathematics which shows that learners did not meet the expectations. After the implementation of Project WAYS, intermediate learners still performed poorly in mathematics which shows that learners still did not meet the expectations. However, if these results will be compared to the pretest before the implementation of Project WAYS, a better performance of intermediate learners can be traced. The study has identified a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results paving the way to reject the null hypothesis and showing proof that Project WAYS is effective in enhancing the mathematical academic performance of intermediate learners in San Miguel Dao I Elementary School.

The following are recommended based from the conclusions of the study: It is recommended that intermediate learners should be provided with ample exercises on reviewing the previous and prerequisite skills to perform better on pretests. It is also suggested for a more robust implementation of Project WAYS and more mathematical exercises and activities for our intermediate learners to ensure better results in mathematics. It is also proposed that Project WAYS be implemented to a larger scale of students, to other subject areas, to other schools and districts posing a similar problem addressed by this study.

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